

Situation 1: Open schools

Use the/the buttons to select your options

Order

Compare

6 additional hours of class per week

3rd dose required for teachers

Quarantine for suspected and confirmed cases of COVID-19

Mandatory use of masks for students

Mandatory COVID self-test for students

Other effects

Health effects on parents and teachers
(number of infections per week per 1000 inhabitants)

5

Primary school students with emotional problems for every 10 students

1

Secondary school students with emotional problems for every 10 students

2

There are approximately 3.8 million primary school students and 2.7 million secondary school students. The learning loss in months for each student would be:

9